

**REPORT ON
FARM TRIALS TO SCREEN APPROPRIATE PULSE AND OILSEED VARIETIES
SUITABLE FOR MONSOON SEASON IN CHHATISGARH**

**VARITAL TRIAL ON FARMER'S FIELD
JUNE/JULY TO OCTOBER/NOVEMBER SEASON - PART-2**

**August, September and October Activities' Report
WITH**

- *Characterization of farmers' varieties*
- *Pulse germplasms characterized for climate adaptation*
- *Knowledge about Climate resilient varieties enhanced*

Submitted on 31 November 2020

Submitted By

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Public Advocacy Initiatives for Rights and Values in India (PAIRVI)

Under

FAO (ITPGR) BSF-IV Cycle Project for India on

Improving pulse biodiversity in rice fallow areas of tribal belts of Central and East Indian states to bring resilience in the farming practice, provide livelihood support and enhance nutritional level of the tribal population

Acknowledgement

We acknowledge with thanks for the contribution of Dr. Geet Sharma, Scientist (Agronomy) in (BTC-CARS) Barrister Thakur Chhedilal College of Agriculture And Research Station, Bilaspur, Chhattisgarh for guiding the farmers. We are thankful to our state coordinator Mr. Shailendra Tiwari from partner NGO- for their dedication and field works. We acknowledge with thanks to farmer Rampad Markam to provide assistance to Mr. Shailendra Tiwari for sowing the varietal trial on farmer's field. Thank you to all for being the pillars of strength and for the tirelessly standing by us in this learning programme during difficult situation (Novel Covid-19).

Chhattisgarh Team - Shri Geet Sharma ji, Shri Pradeep Sharma, Shri Shailndera Tiwari and farmer community

Project Area

Chhattisgarh - District Bilaspur; Block Kota, Villages – Mandalpara, Kadampara, Piparpara. (~10 km²)

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This report is part of the first report which had been submitted along with the activities from May, June, July and August 2020. This report represents the activities of September, October and November 2020.

A. SOWING PERIOD: JUNE-JULY 2020

Reporting Month: SEPTEMBER 2020:

Usually, rainfall occurs in Chhattisgarh till last week of September of first week of October, **but this time the rainfall occurred with high intensity.**

सूखे रहने वाले कई जिलों में इस बार औसत से ज्यादा वर्षा जहां कम पानी होता था, इस बार वहां भी अच्छी बारिश हुई

■ बस्तर की भारी वर्षा से पूरा होता था प्रदेश में मानसूनी बारिश का औसत

छकुनराम खांदव | रावडूर

छत्तीसगढ़ में इस साल मानसून तो अच्छा रहा हो, खास बात ये है कि राज्य में बारिश का औसत इस साल बस्तर की बारिश के भरोसे नहीं रहा। पिछले तीन साल में कई जिले ऐसे हैं, जहां बहुत कम बारिश हो रही थी लेकिन बस्तर में अच्छी बारिश की वजह से प्रदेश की बारिश का औसत सामान्य होता रहा था। लेकिन इस बार सरगुजा को छोड़कर पूरे प्रदेश में पानी एक जैसा ही बरसा है। कहीं कुछ कम तो कहीं कुछ ज्यादा। यहां तक कि रेन शैडो के अन्धे वाले जिले कवर्धा, मुंगेली और बेमेतरा में भी इस बार अच्छी बारिश हो गई है। छत्तीसगढ़ में जून से लेकर 30 सितंबर तक 1234 मिमी बारिश हुई, जो औसत से 8 प्रतिशत अधिक है। जहां तक प्रदेश में बारिश के औसत का सवाल है, पिछले पांच साल से यह सामान्य के आसपास ही है।

लेकिन अंतर यह था कि उत्तर-पश्चिम छत्तीसगढ़ के कुछ हिस्से रेन शैडो एरिया में आते हैं, जिस कारण बारिश उन क्षेत्रों में थोड़ी कम होती रही।

श्रेय: पेज 3

धमतरी: बारिश से गिर गई धान की फसल, खेतों में पानी भरा

धमतरी/कुलदतेज बारिश व हवा के कारण तैयार धान की फसल खेतों में गिर गई है। खेतों में पानी भी भरा है ऐसे में बड़े नुकसान की आशंका जताई जा रही है। जिले में 1.37 लाख हेक्टेयर में धान की फसल ली गई है। इसमें ज्यादातर धान की फसल या तो फसकर तैयार हो गई है या फिर फसल की स्थिति में है। ऐसे में पानी व बारिश से किसानों को बड़े नुकसान की आशंका है। ज्यादा नुकसान कुलद क्षेत्र में होने की आशंका जताई जा रही है।

कम बारिश वाले जिले

जिला	2018	2019	2020
कवर्धा	644.4	893.8	988.2
मुंगेली	835.4	813.7	904.9
बेमेतरा	880.4	971.2	1076.4
दुर्ग	865.8	813.7	1005.5
बलीदाबाजार	915.9	1005.8	1058.3

आज भी बारिश के आसार

मौसम विज्ञानियों के अनुसार छत्तीसगढ़ में शनिवार को भी कहीं-कहीं पर हल्के से मध्यम बारिश होने की संभावना है। एक चक्रीय चक्रवात घेरा इटीय अंधप्रदेश और उसके आसपास 1.5 किलोमीटर ऊंचाई पर है। एक निम्न दाब का क्षेत्र उत्तर अंडमान से और उसके आसपास पूर्व मध्य बंगाल की खाड़ी पर बना है।

News paper, 24.09.2020

Sowing and Germination:

May, June and July

Germination report already submitted in part -1 report.

Number of Plants-stand and 50% Flowering:

20th September

Farm No.-1, 2, 3: Varietal Trial

(Crops: Kulthi, Arhar, Baturi)

Trial Farm No.	Trial Plot No.	No. of plants Stand	% of plants with flower	Any disease observed in plants so far पौधों में कोई बीमारी का दिखाई देना	Water logging बरसात के पानी का भराव	Contact with scientist (Y/N) ...No. Data required for scientist	other vulnerable factors/termites अन्य प्रकार की कोई बात, जो नजर आयी, जैसे - पशु / भारी बरसात / मिट्टी का कटाव/ उर्वरक /
1	1, 3,5,7,9 Kulthi Sargu- ja/Bhaisaj har / rampad Mrakam	46-50%	No data	No	Yes	--	Heavy Rain
2	1,3,5,7,9	45-50 %	No data	No	Yes	--	

3	1,3,5,7,9	45-50%	No data	No	Yes	--	
1	2,4,6,8 Arhar Organic Local seed	40-45%	No data	No	Yes	--	
2	2,4,6,8	45-50%	No data	No	Yes	--	
3	2,4,6,8	55-60%	No data	No	Yes	--	
1	10 Baturi Rachna	20 %	No data	No	Yes	--	
2	10	20%	No data	No	Yes	--	
3	10	20%	No data	No	Yes	--	

Farm No.-4 and 5: Varietal Trial Plot
(Crop: Arhar, Black Sesame)

Trial Farm No.	Trial Plot No.	No. of plants Stand %	% of plants with flower	Any disease observed in plants so far पौधों में कोई बीमारी का दिखाई देना	Water logging बरसात के पानी का भराव	Contact with scientist (Y/N) ...No..... Data required for scientist	other vulnerable factor अन्य प्रकार की कोई बात, जो नजर आयी, जैसे - पशु / termite/ भारी बरसात / मिट्टी का कटाव/ उर्वरक /
4	1, 3,5,7,9 Arhar Organic Local seed	50-60	No Flower	No	Yes	--	Heavy rain
5	1, 3,5,7,9 Arhar Organic Local seed	50-60	No Flower	No	Yes		Heavy rain
4	2,4,6,8 Sesame TKG308	45-50	No Flower	No	Yes		Heavy rain
	11 Sesame Gujrat -I	55	No Flower	No	Yes		Heavy rain
5	2,4,6,8 Sesame TKG308	50-60	No Flower	No	Yes		Heavy rain
	11 Sesame Gujrat -I	55	No Flower	No	Yes		Heavy rain
4	10 Baturi Rachna	30	No Flower	No	Yes		Heavy rain

5	10 Baturi Rachna	30	No Flower	No	Yes		Heavy rain
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Farm No.-6,7,8 and 9: Varietal Trial Plot
(Urad and Moong)

Trial Plot No.	Trial Plot No.	No. of plants Stand	% of plants with flower	Any disease observed in plants so far पौधों में कोई बीमारी का दिखाई देना	Water logging बरसात के पानी का भराव	Contact with scientist (Y/N) ...No.... Data required for scientist	other vulnerable factor अन्य प्रकार की कोई बात, जो नजर आयी, जैसे - पशु / termite/ भारी बरसात / मिट्टी का कटाव/ उर्वरक /
6	1,3,5,7,9 Urad Local Organic Seed	50-55	No	No	Yes	--	Heavy Rain
6	2,4,6,8 Moong Organic Locals eed	50-55	No	No	Yes	--	Heavy Rain
7	1,3 Urad Local Organic Seed	55-60	No	No	Yes	--	Heavy Rain
7	5,7,9 Urad Pratap-1	55-60	No	No	Yes	--	Heavy Rain
6	10 Baturi Rachna	20	No	No	Yes	--	Heavy Rain
7	10 Baturi Rachna	20	No	No	Yes	--	Heavy Rain
8	1, 3, 5, 7, 9 Urad Indra Urad-1	50	No	No	Yes	--	Heavy Rain
8	2,4,6,8 Moong Organic Locals eed	50-55	No	No	Yes	--	Heavy Rain
9	1,3 5, 7, 9 Urad Indra Urad-1	45-50	No	No	Yes	--	Heavy Rain
9	2,4,6,8	45-50	No	No	Yes	--	Heavy Rain

	Moong Organic Locals eed						
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Farm No 6, Urad and Moong

Farm No 5, Sesame and Baturi

Farm No 7, Moong

Trial Farm 8 and 9, Urad and Moong

Trial Farm 11; Rahar and Sesame

Trial Farm 7; Urad

t.f.no.6, t.p.9

Unnamed Road, Bachhali, Chhattisgarh
495442, India

Latitude Longitude
22.306290° 82.084671°

LOCAL 14:45:30 MONDAY 08.24.2020
GMT 09:15:30 ALTITUDE 240 METER

Trial Plot-6,8

t.f.no.6, t.p.9

Unnamed Road, Bachhali, Chhattisgarh
495442, India

Latitude Longitude
22.306290° 82.084671°

LOCAL 14:45:30 MONDAY 08.24.2020
GMT 09:15:30 ALTITUDE 240 METER

Trial Plot 9 and 6

Insect attack on crop

Farm No.-10 and 11: Varietal Trial (Crop : Arhar, Urad and Moong)

Trial Farm No	Trial Plot No.	No. of plants Stand	% of plants with flower	Any disease observed in plants so far पौधो में कोई बीमारी का दिखाई देना	Water logging बरसात के पानी का भराव	Contact with scientist (Y/N) ...YES..... Data required for scientist	other vulnerable factor अन्य प्रकार की कोई बात, जो नजर आयी, जैसे - पशु / termite/ भारी बरसात / मिटटी का कटाव/ उर्वरक /
10	1,4,7 Arhar - Rajiv Lochan	45-50	No flower	No	No	--	Heavy Rain
11	1, 4, 7 Arhar - Rajiv Lochan	45-50	No flower	No	No		
10	2, 5,8 Urad Pratap-1	50-55	No flower	No	No		
11	2, 5,8 Urad Pratap-1	45-50	No flower	No	No		

10	3,6 Moong Local Organic	55	No flower	No	No		
10	9 Moong MH-421	45	No flower	No	No		
11	3,6,9 Moong MH-421	45-50	No flower	No	No		

Pod and Harvesting: October

Farm No.-1, 2, 3: Varietal Trial (Crops: Kulthi, Arhar, Baturi)

Trial Farm No.	Trial Plot No.	Pod appearing date/	Number of seeds per pod	No. of pod in a plant	Any disease observed in plants so far	Harvesting of pods	Quantity (kg)of pod got from trial plot	Contact with scientist (Y) ...Yes..... Data required for scientist	Other Vulnerable Factor
1	1, 3,5,7,9 Kulthi Sarguja/Bhaisajhar / rampad Mrakam	4/09/20	4	4-5	No	30/09/20	200 gm	--	Heavy Rain
2	1,3,5,7,9	24/09/20	4-5	4	No	13/10/20	200 gm	--	
3	1,3,5,7,9	24/09/20		No data	No	15/10/20	200 gm	--	
1	2,4,6,8 Arhar Organic Local seed	4/09/20	No data	No data	No	30/02/21	200 gm	--	
2	2,4,6,8	24/09/20	No data	No data	No	0/02/21	250 gm	--	
3	2,4,6,8	24/09/20	No data	No data	No	0/02/21	200 gm	--	
1	10 Baturi Rachna	4/09/20	No data	No data	No	30/09/20	200 gm	--	
2	10	24/09/20	No data	No data	No	13/10/20	200 gm	--	
3	10	24/09/20	No data	No data	No	15/10/20	200 gm	--	

Farm No.-4 and 5: Varietal Trial Plot
(Crop: Arhar, Black Sesame)

Trial Farm No.	Trial Plot No.	Pod appearing date/	Number of seeds per pod	No. of pod in a plant	Any disease observed in plants so far	Harvesting of pods	Quantity (kg)of pod got from trial plot	Contact with scientist (Y) ...Yes..... Data required for scientist	Other Vulnerable Factor
4	1, 3,5,7,9 Arhar Organic Local seed	8/10/20	4-5	No data	No	28/03/21	200 gm	--	Heavy Rain
5	1, 3,5,7,9 Arhar Organic Local seed	8/10/20	4-5	No data		28/03/21	200 gm		
4	2,4,6,8 Sesame TKG308	8/10/20	0	No data		0	0		
	11 Sesame Gujrat -I	8/10/20	4-5	No data		0	0		
5	2,4,6,8 Sesame TKG308	8/10/20	0	No data		0	0		
	11 Sesame Gujrat -I	8/10/20	0	No data		0	0		
4	10 Baturi Rachna	8/10/20	No data	No data		28/10/21	200 gm		
5	10 Baturi Rachna	8/10/20	No data	No data		28/10/21	200 gm		

Farm No.-6,7,8 and 9: Varietal Trial Plot
(Urad and Moong)

Trial Farm No.	Trial Plot No.	Pod appearing date/	Number of seeds per pod	No. of pod in a plant	Any disease observed in plants so far	Harvesting of pods	Quantity (kg)of pod got from trial plot	Contact with scientist (Y) ...Yes..... Data required for scientist	Other Vulnerable Factor
6	1,3,5,7,9 Urad Local	4/09/20	No data	No data	No	30/09/20	100 gm	---	Heavy Rain

	Organic Seed								
6	2,4,6,8 Moong Organic Locals eed	4/09/20	No data	No data		30/09/20	100 gm		
7	1,3 Urad Local Organic Seed	4/09/20	No data	No data		30/09/20	100 gm		
7	5,7,9 Urad Pratap-1	4/09/20	No data	No data		30/09/20	100 gm		
6	10 Baturi Rachna	4/09/20	No data	No data		30/09/20	100 gm		
7	10 Baturi Rachna	4/09/20	No data	No data		30/09/20	100 gm		
8	1, 3, 5,7,9 Urad Indra Urad-1	8/10/20	No data	No data		20/10/20	100 gm		
8	2,4,6,8 Moong Organic Locals eed	8/10/20	No data	No data		20/10/20	100 gm		
9	1,3 5, 7,9 Urad Indra Urad-1	8/10/20	No data	No data		20/10/20	100 gm		
9	2,4,6,8 Moong Organic Locals eed	8/10/20	No data	No data		20/10/20	100 gm		

Farm No.-10 and 11: Varietal Trial
(Crop : Arhar, Urad and Moong)

Trial Farm No.	Trial Plot No.	Pod appearing date/	Number of seeds per pod	No. of pod in a plant	Any disease observed in plants so far	Harvesting of pods	Quantity (kg)of pod got from trial plot 200 gm	Contact with scientist (Y) ...Yes..... Data required for scientist	Other Vulnerable Factor
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10	1,4,7 Arhar - Rajiv Lochan	Data Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	No	25/02/2021	200 gm	Yes	Heavy Rain
11	1, 4, 7 Arhar - Rajiv Lochan	Data Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	No	25/02/2021	200 gm		
10	2, 5,8 Urad Pratap-1	10/10/20	Not Available	Not Available	No	20/10/20	200 gm		
11	2, 5,8 Urad Pratap-1	10/10/20	Not Available	Not Available	No	20/10/20	200 gm		
10	3,6 Moong Local Organic	10/10/20	Not Available	Not Available	No	20/10/20	200 gm		
10	9 Moong MH-421	10/10/20	Not Available	Not Available	No	20/10/20	200 gm		
11	3,6,9 Moong MH-421	10/10/20	Not Available	Not Available	No	20/10/20	200 gm		

Overall summary:

Similar Varieties:

Crop	Similar varieties			Similar varieties		Scientific Variety (S.V.)		Project Result	No. of Varieties
	Farmer Variety	Farmer Variety	Farmer Variety	Farmer Variety	Farmer Variety	S.V-1	S.V-2		
Kulthi	Kulthi Sarguja/Bhaisajhar / rampad Mrakam 1,2,3* a								a
Arhar		Arhar Organic Local seed 1,2,3,4,5* a				Arhar - Rajiv Lochan b			a b
Sesame						Sesame TKG308 a	Sesame Gujrat - I b		a b
Urad	Urad Local Organic Seed a					Urad Pratap-1 b	Urad Indra Urad-1 c		a b c

Moong	Moong Local Organic a				Moong MH-421 b			a b
Baturi		Baturi Rachna 1,2,3* a						a

*star denoted the trial farm number.

Characteristics Identified by Farmers for trial's varieties

Crop	Serial No. of Identified Varieties	Identified Varieties	Type of varieties	Characteristics Identified by Farmers				
				Productivity (Serial No. of identified Variety)	Taste and Digestive (Serial No. of identified Variety)	Insect Resistance	Resistance/requirement	Grain size and any other
Kulthi	1	Sarguja / Farmer Variety	Local					Small size seed, brown/black color seed.
Arhar	1	Organic Local Farmer variety	Local		--	-	-	
	2	Rajiv Lochan	Improved		-	-	-	
Sesame	1	TKG308	Improved		-	-		
	2	Gujrat-1	Improved					
Urad	1	Local Organic Seed	Desi/Local Varieties					
	2	Pratap-1	Improved Variety					
	3	Indra Urad-1	Improved Variety					
Moong	1	Local Organic	Local					
	2	MH 421	Improved Variety					

Baturi	1	Rachana	Local					
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Suitable time for sowing

S. No.	Crop Name	Suitable Sowing time	Traditional Knowledge: Indicator
1	Kulthi	20-25 th June 15 June -15 July 2 July-8 July Rain start-10 July	3 Day later of Jagannath Yatra / Harisen Festival
2	Arhar	-	3 Day later of Jagannath Yatra
3	Sesame	20-25 th June	3 Day later of Jagannath Yatra
4.	Urad	20-25 th June	3 Day later of Jagannath Yatra
5.	Moong	20-25 th June	3 Day later of Jagannath Yatra
6.	Baturi	20-25 th June	3 Day later of Jagannath Yatra

1. Collection of Sample-Pod for Scientific Observation

S. No.	Trial Farm No.	Trial Plot No.	Number of Pod for sample (Average) from each trial plot	Packaging and labeling (Crop Name, Trial Farm No. and Trial Plot No.)	Submitted to scientist
1				Kulthi	No
2				Arhar	No
3				Sesame	No
4				Urad	No
				Baturi	No
				Moong	No

Reporting Month: **OCTOBER 2020:**

Selection of appropriate varieties for next year (2021):

Showing date	T.F. No.	T.P. No.	Farmer's Trial plot name	Local/ KVK variety name	Identified Farmer's Variety Name	Crop name	Seeds are appropriate for using in next year – YES/NO	Qt.* of Seed in Community Seed Bank
				Local variety	Sarguja	Kulthi	Yes	3 kg
				Local	Organic	Arhar	Yes	2
				Improved	Rajiv Lochan	Arhar	Yes	1
				Total Seed				
				Improved	TKG 308	Sesame	No	1
				Improved	Gujrat I	Sesame	No	2
				Total Seed				
				Local	Local	Urad	Yes	1.5
				Improved	Pratap-I	Urad	Yes	1
				Improved	Indra I	Urad	Yes	2

				Improved	Rachana	Baturi	Yes	2
				Local	Organic	Moong	Yes	1
				Improved	MH 421	Moong	Yes	1

- Total 17.5 kg of Pulses and oil seed received in Community Seed Bank for June-July sowing.

*-Total quantity represents the total seeds, which have been received from trial plots and passbook's beneficiaries. The data taken from community seed bank's ledger and passbook.

Fig.-Distribution of Seed